

Board Structure and Dividend Payout Policies of Listed Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study basically investigates the effect of board structure on dividend policy of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. It also looks at the relationship between Dividend Payout ratio, board size, board composition and profitability the sampled consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study utilizes secondary method of data collection to collect the data necessary for the conduct of this study. Data were collected from the annual reports of the six sampled firms for the period 2013-2023. Ex-post factor research design was used as well as the pooled regression analysis method was employed as a statistical technique for analyzing the data collected. The study revealed that there is an insignificant association between dividend payout ratio and board size of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. In another light the result of the study gave a contrary opinion where it indicates that dividend payout ratio, profitability and board composition of the sampled consumer goods firms in Nigeria are all significant related. The study recommends that since profitability and board composition are statistically significant and they affect dividend payout of the listed consumer goods firm in Nigeria for the period of the study, the management of the entities should focus on building more profitability and also ensure regular portfolio analysis while taking into consideration other factors that can affect the company's profitability in the long run.

Key word: Board structure, Dividend payout policy, Board size, Board Composition, Profitability.

1.1 Introduction

It is generally accepted that corporate boards plays a fundamental role in corporate governance. The structure of these strategic dimensions of the company involves determining what amount of profit is distributed by the company to shareholders and what should be reserve for future expansion. The listing rules of Nigeria exchange group and the provisions of section 65 of CAMA 2020, state that the management of a corporate organization is separated from their ownership. The agency theory suggests that when ownership is separated from control, conflict of interest emanate between the shareholders and management as a result of pay out policy and other incentives

(Jensen 1986). This leads to a situation where by useful decisions such as financial policy is delegated to management. The management decisions concerning the dividend payment may not always be in the interest of all classes of shareholders since management may wish to invest substantially in an asset to expand the scale of their operation. Shareholders, on the other hand, may prefer getting more from the earnings in form of cash dividend (Tijjani & Sani, 2016). Jensen and Meckling (1978) state that one way to reduce agency conflict is to pay a higher proportion of earning as a dividend to shareholders. Abdulkadir (2015) document that one key aspect of shareholders wealth maximization is payment of regular and sustainable dividend payout.

Dividend policy is the decision of the companies' managements to distribute profits to shareholders as dividends or to retain it in the form of retained earnings to finance future investments (Putri & Rokhim, 2016). In other word, dividend policy refers to the set of rules or norms that a company follows to decide how much of its profit it will pay out to shareholders and how much of the profit they will reinvest (Widyasti & DwijaPutri, 2021). The choice of paying dividends is ultimately decided by the board of directors of the company, and once dividends have been declared, it becomes a debt to the firm and cannot be overturned easily (Firer, *et al.*, 2012). The dividend policy of a company is reflected in the dividend pay-out ratio which is the percentage of earnings distributed in the form of cash dividends, this means that, the size of the dividend pay-out ratio will affect the investment decisions of shareholders and also the company's financial condition (Sakir & Fadli, 2014). Dividend policy is an influential control mechanism to reduce the conflict of interest between management and shareholders, as management will want low dividend distribution that will provide benefit to them as managers, while shareholders will want their profits to be divided in the form of dividends (Ullah *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, dividend policy decision is one of the most important decisions taken by the top management of companies (Kulathunga & Azeez, 2015). Dividend payout as an area of financial management has been the subject of several controversies and a major concern in the corporate finance literature for both developed and developing market (Sarwar *et al.*, 2018). Dividend policy remains one of the most important financial policies not only from the view point of the companies but also from that of the shareholders, potential investors, consumers, regulatory bodies, employees, as well as the government (Onumoh, 2019).

Wealth creation in a capitalist economy like Nigeria is based on trust. Investors invest their resources in companies and they (companies) produce goods and services that benefit the nation as a whole. Good investment decision is based on information provided by organizations to existing and potential shareholders (Ali & Anwar, 2021). Therefore, good information provided is essential to effective growth of capital markets and a productive allocation to economic resources. The investor must have confidence in the financial information provided before they can invest their resources and this is largely dependent on availability of accurate and timely reliable information. It is matters of great concern to parties who are interested in the financial statements of entities when the system cannot be relied on as a result of craftiness of financial managers to deliver inaccurate information to enable investor evaluate the investment opportunities.

Board structure is substantially central in achieving and maintaining shareholders trust and confidence especially in financial decisions. Nevertheless corporate business environment around the world has experienced cases of damage caused by poor board structure which brought about doubts in the mind of the owners and the general public (Johle *et al.*, 2015). In practical, it is often believed that the interest of the board of directors are often in contrast with that of the company's

shareholders, while the interest of the company's directors is often considered to be living large and spending extravagantly from the wealth accumulations of these companies, that of the shareholders is wealth maximization which comes from the reinvestment of company's profit which accumulates wealth in the long run.

Studies however, has revealed that firms with poor board structure have poor performance rate, while those with good board structure are likely to have good performance rate (Edward & Samuel, 2011). This however may have positive or negative impact on financial decisions which in turn may determine the amount of dividend payout to be given to the shareholders. A number of other useful researches such as Azar, *et al.* (2014), Ghabaye (2012), Bathula (2008), examine board characteristics on shareholders wealth. In other vein Sarwar *et al.* (2018), Pelt (2013), Bolbol (2012), Subramaniam and Devi (2011) examine board characteristics and dividend payout ratio. Furthermore, there are still debates in regards to the relationship between board structure and the role it facilitate in the formulation of dividend policies especially with regards to the amount of dividend entitlements of shareholders (Sarwar *et al.*, 2018).

The stock market being the regulatory body that oversee, coordinate and measures the health of the economy (Bhowmik & Wang, 2020), has over time experienced these issues directly related to board structure such as the agency conflict of interest between the board of a company and its shareholders. The reoccurrence of accounting scandals, stock market crash, fall in prices of stock in the capital markets, heightened volatility of stock markets despite the robust of the financial statements has called for concern. Wasu *et al.* (2020), opine that if the performances of each sector in terms of value relevance are known, it will enable the regulators and users of accounting information to narrow down to the sector facing the above challenges.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The central objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between board structure and dividend payout of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Other specific objectives are:

- To ascertain the relationship between board composition and dividend payout policy of consumers' goods firms in Nigeria.
- To examine the effect of board size on dividend payout policy of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria.
- To ascertain whether firms profitability has significant effect in influencing investment decisions of shareholders of listed consumers' good firms in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

Base on the above objective the following hypotheses are formulated for this study:

H₀₁: Board composition does not have a significant impact on dividend payout policies of consumers' goods firms in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Board size does not have significant impact on dividend payout policy of consumers' goods firms in Nigeria.

H03: Firm profitability does not have significant on dividend payout policy of listed consumer good firm in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

This section of the study reviewed the relevant concepts of dividend payout policy, board structure, the theoretical overview of the underpinning theories and the empirical reviewed of previous studies.

2.1 Conceptual Literature

Dividend is that portion of net profit which is distributed among the shareholders. The dividend decision of the firm is of crucial importance for the finance manager since it determines the amount to be distributed among shareholders and the amount of profit to be retained in the business (Onumoh, 2019).

The size of the board is the total number of board members comprising of executive directors, non-executive directors, independent directors and gray directors in a company (Muhammad & Aishat, 2020). Jensen, (1993) stated that smaller board size can be monitor effectively. Thus conclude that firm with the smaller board have capacity to be monitored and can take financial decisions.

Board composition is the proportion of non-executive directors to the total number of directors on the board. Yusoff and Adamu,(2012) as cited by Muhammad and Aishat (2020), affirm that the board of directors bear the ultimate responsibility for preventing negative management practices that may lead to corporate failures but also ensure that firms take advantage of opportunities that I prove shareholders wealth.

2.2 Theoretical Frame Work

The underpinning theory for this study was Agency cost theory. This theory was carefully selected to be able to give a strong base for this study.

Agency Cost Theory: according to Putri and Rokhim, (2016) agency cost is a cost that will arise or opportunity that will be loss because of conflict in a company (agency problem). One example of agency problem is the conflict between managers and the owners which are the shareholders and it is in relation to the company's dividend. Managers may not always adopt a dividend policy that is more profitable to shareholders but would prefer to develop a dividend policy that maximizes their own private benefits and personal interests. Since shareholders are aware of this fact, they may develop means of controlling manager behaviors (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) and (Jensen, 1986).

2.3 Empirical Review

Dividend policy has been analyzed for many decades, but no universally accepted explanation for companies observed dividend behaviors has been established (Samuel & Edward, 2011). It remains one of the top most difficult unsolved problems in financial economics.

Subramaniam and Devis (2011) studied on corporate governance and dividend policy in Malaysia, suggests that dividend and investment opportunity are low in the presence of larger board size and composition. In the study of Shah, Ullah *et al.* (2011) investigated the relationship between

corporate governance, ownership structure and dividend performance of 23 listed firms at Ghana stock exchange for a period of six years ranging from 2002-2007. The findings indicate a positive impact of board size on dividend policy, while there is a negative (significant) impact of ownership structure on dividend policy. Gill & Obradovich (2012) examine the impact of corporate governance and institutional ownership on dividend payment decisions. By using a sample of 296 US listed firms, they find a positive effect of board size and CEO duality on dividend payment. Uwalomwa *et al.*, (2012), examines the relationship between financial performance and dividend payout among listed firms in Nigeria, it also looked at the relationship between ownership structure, size of firms and the dividend payouts. Annual reports for the period ranging from 2006 to 2010 were gathered using secondary method of data collection from a sample of fifty firms. Regression analysis method was employed as a statistical tool for analyzing the data collected. The study revealed that there is a significant positive association between the performance of firms and the dividend payout of the sampled firms in Nigeria. It also revealed that ownership structure and firms' size has significant impact on dividend payout of firms as well.

Odia and Ogiedu (2013), investigated the relationship between dividend payout policy, agency and corporate governance in Nigeria using a sample of thirty listed companies randomly selected from companies listed in the Nigeria stock exchange from 2006 to 2010. The study adopted a panel OLS regression analysis in determining the relationship between payout, agency conflict and corporate governance. Their result shows that insider and institutional ownership has a positive but insignificant impact on dividend payout. They also showed that firm's investment opportunities and leverage have significant impact on the dividend payout. From the result they concluded that insiders and institutional ownership may not completely mitigate the agency conflict associated with effective dividend payout policy. Velnampy, (2013), in his study of corporate governance and firm's performance used a sample of twenty eight firms from the period between 2007 to 2011; found that determinants of corporate governance are not correlated to the performance measures of the organization. Regression model showed that corporate governance doesn't affect companies. ROE and ROA revealed that corporate governance measure are not correlated with performance measure.

Uwuigbe (2014) examined the determinants of dividends policy in the Nigerian stock exchange market. The study selected a total of 50 listed firms in the Nigerian stock exchange market using the judgmental sampling technique. Also, data was collected from the corporate annual reports of the sampled companies for the period 2006-2011. The paper was basically modeled to examine the effects of financial performance of firms, firm size, financial leverage and board independence on the dividend payout decisions of listed firms operating in the Nigerian stock exchange market using the regression analysis method. The study find out that there is a significant positive relationship between firms' financial performance, size of firms and board independence on the dividend payouts decisions of listed firms in Nigeria.

Musa, (2014) studied the relationship between corporate governance and dividend payout ratio, the study identified that corporate governance mechanism such as board size and composition has a negative influence on the dividend payout ratio. Bako, (2015), examined the impact of ownership structure on dividend policy of firms listed in the Nigeria consumer goods industry. The study used the ex-post facto research design. Data were collected from secondary source using the annual reports and accounts of sampled companies and was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regression methods. The study finds that insider ownership has negative

and insignificant impact on dividend per share (DPS) of consumer goods industry and suggesting that little attention should be given to ownership structure. Dandago *et al.*, (2015), also examined the relationship between corporate shareholding structure and dividend payout ratio of listed chemical and paint companies in Nigeria stock exchange over the period of 2008 to 2013. An ex-post facto research design and multiple regression analysis were employed. The result revealed that managerial shareholding has a negative and significant impact on the dividend payout ratio of chemical and paint companies in Nigeria this study was inconsistent with that of Bako, (2015).

Elmi and Muturi (2016) investigated the effects of profitability on dividend payout by Nairobi Securities Exchange-listed commercial and service firms (NSE) The scope of their research covered a 10-year period from 2005 to 2014, and the study used both primary and secondary data as the foundation for their analysis. They contended that respondents believed that when a company's profitability fell, it reduced its dividend payout. They also discovered that respondents agreed that dividend decisions provide investors with information about the company's profitability. Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that when the profitability of the surveyed firms suffers, the dividends payable are reduced. The study findings also revealed that when the surveyed companies forecast high profit growth, they demonstrate it to their investors by paying out large dividends. Despite the fact that changes in profitability had a positive effect on dividend payout, the results revealed no significant effect of profitability on dividend payout? This means that changes in profitability are unlikely to have a large impact on dividend payout. Dividend decisions, on the other hand, provide investors with information about the company's profitability.

Shahid *et al.* (2016) conducted a study on ownership structure, board size, board composition and dividend policy from two emerging markets. The study aim at examining the potential relationship between ownership structure, board size, board composition, CEO duality and dividend policy of 176 listed firms at KSE and 280 listed firms at BSI from 2010 to 2015. Pooled ordinary least square regression was used to analyze the relationship between corporate governance determinants and dividend policy. The finding of the study showed that positive association exists between managerial ownership, board size board composition and dividend policy. The study also found a negative relationship between ownership concentration and dividend policy.

Okafor *et al.* (2016), examined the effect of board interest (insider ownership) on dividend payout of the Nigerian manufacturing sectors for the period of 2009 to 2015. The data for the study was generated from the annual report of five randomly selected firms from the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria economy. The data for this study was analyzed using pooled panel least square model and the result revealed that board interest has a negative and insignificant impact on dividend payout of the firms under consideration. On the other hand the result of the correlation test shows that board interest has a negative relationship with dividend payout. The empirical result also indicates that ownership concentration has a positive but insignificant effect on dividend payout of the Nigerian manufacturing firms. Firm size was found to have a positive and significant effect on dividend payout among Nigerian manufacturing firms. The study suggested that firms in the sector should balance the use of both insider ownership and dividend pay as a tool for managing agency conflict which always result to increased agency cost provided that the choice of tool will not adversely affect the firm's performance.

Armaya'u and Awaisu, (2017), conducted a study to examine the impact of corporate board attributes on dividend policy of listed deposit money bank in Nigeria. The data was collected from

annual report and accounts using secondary data of the sampled companies for the period from 2006 to 2015. Data is analyzed by means of descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and panel data regression technique was used to analyze the data, the variable tested include board size, board composition, audit committee size and managerial ownership. The result found that board size, board composition and ownership structure have significant negative impact on dividend policy of listed deposit money bank in Nigeria, and audit committee is statistically insignificant. The study recommends the needs for regulatory agencies to strengthen the corporate governance mechanism especially the power of audit committee.

Muhammad and Aishat, (2020), examined both the direct and indirect effect of board characteristics, dividend policy and shareholders wealth of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2008 to 2018. The study used path analysis to analyse the all data obtained during the study. The data were obtained from secondary means, from the financial statement of fifty one companies while using dividend policy as their mediating factor. It was found that board characteristics can significantly improve shareholders wealth by using dividend. They believe that firms should restructure their dividend policies for the improvement of shareholders wealth.

The overall findings from this reviewed suggest that board structure revealed mixed and inconclusive results as some of the studies shows positive and significant while other revealed a negative and insignificant impact on dividend policy.

3. Methodology

Panel survey type of longitudinal research design was used for this study. This study is based on the positivists' paradigms, as the study is quantitative in nature and it will adopt secondary source of data. The data have been collected from the annual report and financial statement of the sampled listed consumer good firms in Nigeria. The population of this study consists of all the consumer goods firms listed on Nigerian exchange group as at the period of the study. This study sampled listed consumer good firms base on simple random sampling where ten (10) companies have been selected as sample size. This companies include 7 Up Nigeria place, cardbury Nig. Place, Flour Mills Nig. Plc, Honeywell flour Mills plc. Unilever Nig. Place, Nascon allied industries plc, Nestle Nig. Plc, Guinness Nigeria plc, Champion Breweries plc, and international Breweries plc. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and regression analysis.

Variable and their measurement

Table 3.1

Dependent variable	Measurement
Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR)	Is computed as the ratio of DPS to EPS Mohammad and Aisha (2020)
Independent Variable	
Board Size (BS)	Numbers of Directors on the board Mohammad and Aisha (2020).
Board Composition (BC)	The numbers of non-executive directors to the numbers of executive directors, Anderson and Reeb (2003).

Profitability (PROF) Is computed as profit after tax divided by the company's equity. Saheed and Aishat (2017).

Source: *generated by the researcher from literatures.*

Model Specification

For the purpose of this study the researchers develop this model for the dependent and independent variables:

$$DPR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 PROF_{it} + \beta_3 BC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

DPR=Dividend Payout Ratio

BS= Board Size

PROF= Profitability

BC= Board Composition

ε = Error term

It= time dimension of the variables

β_0 = Constant or intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Beta Coefficients to be estimated.

Result and Discussion of Findings

This section discusses the results of the model estimated by the study.

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4.1 summary of descriptive statistics

Variables	N	Mean	Standard deviation
Dividend payout ratio	110	0.7164	0.70402
Board size	110	9.3364	2.14723
Profitability	110	0.3168	0.40238
Board composition	110	4.1992	2.51985

Source: *SPSS22 (2024)*

Table 4.1 above show the Descriptive statistics of the variable used in the regression model. This show the average of the variable computed from the financial statements.

The average dividend payout ratio is 0.7164. This means on an average the firm's pay approximately 72% of their profit as dividend. The standard deviation of 0.70402 show that there is a minimal gap between the earnings and dividend payout.

The average board size is 9.3364. This means that the firms differ in their board size compared with the standard deviation of 2.14723.

The average profitability is 0.3168. This means on an average the firms earned approximately 32% profits. Therefore there is more money available to be distributed to shareholders as dividend. The standard deviation of 0.40238 means there is a great variation in profitability amongst the sampled firms during the period under study. The average board composition is 4.1992 this means that the firms have more non -executive directors than executive directors on board.

4.2 Pearson correlation

Table 4.2 summary of Pearson correlation

Variables	DPR	BS	PROF	BC
DPR	1.00			
BS	-0.33	1.00		
PROF	0.66	-0.12	1.00	
BC	-0.23	0.54	-0.12	1.00

Source: *SPSS 22 (2024)*

Table 4.2 above shows the correlation relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. The table presents the result of correlation on dividend payout ratio, board size, profitability and board composition for the sampled firms.

The relationship between dividend payout ratio and board size (-0.33) show negative and insignificant relationship, as it is greater than 0.050 level of significant; profitability and dividend payout as deduce from the table is (0.66) which is positively correlated but insignificant has it is greater than 0.050 level of significant; and board composition and dividend payout ratio (-0.23) which is negatively correlated and the relationship is insignificant at 0.050 level of significant.

4.3 Regression Analysis

Table 4.3. Summary of regression analysis

variable	Beta	Std error	Beta	T-stat	P>/T/
Board size	-0.096	0.036	-0.292	-2.678	0.009
Profitability	0.038	0.162	0.022	0.235	0.814
Board composition	-0.019	0.030	-0.067	-0619	0.537

Source: *SPSS 22 (2024)*

It can be deduced from the table 4.3 above, that negative relationship exists between dividend payout and board size of the listed firms. However the relationship is significant as reflected by the p value (0.009), as 0.009 is less than 0.050 level of significant.

It can be deduced that a positive relationship exist between profitability and dividend payout of the listed firms. However the relationship is insignificant as reflected by the T (0.235) and sig value (p-value) 0.814 which is greater than 0.050 level of significant. And finally it can be deduced that a negative relationship exist between dividend payout and board composition of the listed firms. However the relationship is insignificant as reflected by the T (-0.619) and sig value (p-value) 0.537.

Test of Hypothesis

The findings from the result of this study indicates that the first hypothesis of this study which state that; Board composition does not have significant impact on dividend payout ratio of consumers goods firms in Nigeria should be accepted this is because from table 4.3 above, it is discover that board composition does not have significant impact on consumer goods firms dividend payout as reflected by the sig (0.537), which is greater than the 0.050 level of significance. Therefore the study failed to reject the hypothesis. The study finding support the finding of Subraimanian and Devis, (2011)

The second hypothesis for this study which indicates that Board Size does not have a significant effect on dividend payout of a consumer goods firms will be rejected this is because from the result in table 4.3 above it is discover that board size have significant impact on consumer good firms dividend payout as reflected by the sig (0.009), which is less than 0.050 level of significant. Therefore the study fails to reject the hypothesis. The study support the study conducted by Mohammed and Aishat, (2020), Armaya'u a and Awaisu, (2017), Musa, (2014) and contrary to the study conducted by Shahid *et al.* (2016).

Finally the hypothesis which state that Firm profitability does not have significant impact on dividend payout of consumer's goods firms in Nigeria was accepted. It can be deduced from table 4.3 above that profitability does not have significant impact on consumer goods firms' dividend payout as reflected by the sig (0.814), which is greater than 0.050 level of significant. Therefore the hypothesis will be rejected. This finding is contrary to the study conducted by Elmi and Muturi (2016), which stated that profitability has a significant effect on dividend policy.

Conclusion and Recommendation

From the results and findings from this study, it is safe to say that there is a relationship between board structure and dividend policies of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The researcher comes to a conclusion that, profitability and board composition are very essential players in the formulation of dividend payout policy. However, the result presents a different view in regards to board size the implication is that board size has no significant effect on dividend payout policies of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Having expected some various findings associated with dividend payout and board structure. On the basis of the study it is essential to come up with some recommendation

For the purpose of this study, the following recommendations are given.

Shareholder should put more focus on the profitability of the companies they invest in and try to guide it from any form of misrepresentation.

It is important for an investor not to only know how well his investments do in relation to other investment but also to understand how well his investments in line with general policies of the company. It is also important for him or her to diversify his investments are. This research therefore recommends regular portfolio analysis.

Companies should monitor their board structure because it has impact on the growth and development of the company, and its dividend payout policy.

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